

THE EFFECT OF TEACHERS' ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIORS AND STRESS LEVELS ON SCHOOL EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract:

The current study examined the relationship between school effectiveness and teachers' demographic characteristics, organizational citizenship behaviors and stress, and the effects of teachers' demographic characteristics, organizational citizenship behaviors and stress levels on school effectiveness. Within the scope of the research, a causal comparison model was used and the opinions of 222 Turkish teachers who were working in the schools were evaluated. According to the results, school effectiveness was significantly and positively correlated with all dimensions of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviors, and significantly and negatively correlated with stress. In addition, it was found that the demographic characteristics were not a significant predictor of school effectiveness but only the seniority variable was a significant predictor of school effectiveness and it was found that the stress and dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior were significant predictors of school effectiveness.

Keywords: organizational citizenship behaviors; stress; school effectiveness; teachers

1. Introduction

Each organization has a number of aims with respect to its existence. Barnard (1938) defines the level of attainment of these goals as "effectiveness" (Balci, 2013, p.1). As an organization, schools also have a number of goals and effectiveness levels. The concept of school effectiveness is explained by many models developed with different perspectives. According to a model, while school effectiveness is defined according to the degree of reaching the designated goals, in another model it is explained by the satisfaction of the education stakeholders such as teachers, students, managers, parents

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(Balci, 2013). When these models are examined, it is seen that school effectiveness is not a variable that can be measured only by one factor. As a result, the effectiveness of school which is defined as an open social system, is closely related to all of the input-process-output components (Hoy & Miskel, 2012). Teacher also included in these components; is one of the factors affecting school effectiveness (Balci, 2013).

Since schools are complex structures, it seems difficult to conceptualize school effectiveness. The effectiveness of schools is directly proportional to the goal of the school. However, the school differs according to each stakeholder for the purposes of the school, since different stakeholders have different expectations from the school. It is also difficult to determine the effectiveness of schools because of the difficulties in measuring the quality of school outputs. When it comes to school, the concept of effectiveness comes first as standardized tests. Because almost everyone acknowledges that basic skills that students need to earn are an important part of an effective school. Factors such as managerial function, leadership behaviors, morale, trust level, culture and climate, parental involvement, community support, teacher competence and teacher loyalty, commitment and job satisfaction are very important factors in terms of school effectiveness (Uline, Miller, & Tschannen-Moran, 1998). All these factors, as well as the fact that teachers show organizational citizenship behavior, will undoubtedly be an important factor for effective school structure.

When literature is examined, it was revealed that there are many factors that affect organizational effectiveness. For example, it is possible to find out the studies on organizational health and organizational climate as a predictor of organizational effectiveness (e.g. Korkmaz, 2011), principals' effective leadership qualities and school effectiveness (e.g. Yilmaz, 2010; Bolanle, 2013; Cerit & Yildirim, 2017), researches on relationship between school culture and school effectiveness (e.g. Ayik & Ada, 2007; Sezgin, 2010; Senel & Buluc, 2016). School effectiveness and job satisfaction (e.g. Yildirim, Akan, & Yalcin, 2017), and the effect of organizational commitment on organizational effectiveness (e.g. Ak, 2017). There are also some studies (e.g. Alanoglu, 2014, Alanoglu & Demirtas, 2016, Gokmen, 2011, Miles, Borman, Spector, & Fox, 2002, Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Paine & Bacharach, 2000 ; Somech & Ron, 2007; Van Der Vegt, Van De Vliert & Oosterhof, 2003) showing that there is a positive and meaningful relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and school effectiveness.

Organizational citizenship behavior is a concept that defines the voluntary undertaking of behaviors that are not part of an employee's job and are not rewarded by the organization (Jain & Cooper, 2012). Organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB) are behaviors that are desired to be shown within the organization and increase organizational effectiveness (Organ, 1997). It is expected that these behaviors, which represent behaviors beyond the organizational role of the organization formally, increase their effectiveness and commitment (Hodson, 2002). OCB that contribute to enhancing individual and organizational performance can increase practically the efficacy and efficiency of the organizations (Podsakoff & MacKenzie, 1994). It is thought that OCB have an important influence on group efficiency and productivity as well as on overall productivity of the organization (Srivastava & Saldanha, 2008). Thus, OCB of

employees are very important situation in terms of the organizations. Bogler and Somech (2005) suggest that OCB for students helped the school become an effective school.

It is not expected that schools will achieve their goals through only formally identified teacher roles (George & Brief, 1992). Teachers are expected to make professional decisions based on their work and to assume complex roles that vary according to the situation. Therefore, teachers' demonstration of organizational citizenship behavior is very important in terms of realizing the purpose of the school. The concept of organizational citizenship behavior first entered the business administration literature in 1983 (Bateman ve Organ, 1983; Gurbuz & Yuksel, 2011). Organ (1988) defined the organizational citizenship behavior as an effort and extra-role behavior that is discretionary beyond the standards and job descriptions that are set for the individual in the working environment.

Research on organizational citizenship behavior is generally also based on the classification by Organ (1988). The classification of the Organ comes from the five dimensions of altruism, conscience, courtesy, sportsmanship, and civic virtue, and is the most accepted and used classification in the field. *Altruism*, auxiliary behaviors towards specific individuals, *conscientiousness* going beyond the minimum level of participation required, *sportsmanship* is tolerance of inevitable incidents without being present in the shit, *courtesy* to inform others to prevent job problems and *civic virtue* describes the interest and concern of the organizational life (Srivastava & Saldanha, 2008).

One of the other important dimensions of organizational behavior, such as organizational citizenship behavior, is stress (Tambe & Shanker, 2015). Stress is a dynamic situation that creates an intense and distressing result in people and that significantly affects human behavior. Although stress is usually approached in a negative frame, stress is not exactly a bad mental state. In recent years, researchers have begun to address the two sources of stress encouraging and prohibitive. While workload is defined as the task of completing tasks and stress sources that promote time urgency, role uncertainty, role conflict, extreme workload, job insecurity, environmental uncertainties cause prohibitive stress sources. Stress shows itself with physiological symptoms such as headache and high blood pressure psychological symptoms such as anxiety, depression and reduction in job satisfaction (Judge and Robins, 2013) and behavioral symptoms such as not coming to work and changing work (De Croon, Sluiter, Blonk, Broersen, & Frings-Dresen, 2004) itself. In addition, in many researches that examine the relationship between stress and job performance, it is stated that the relationship between two variables is a bell curve or inverse U shape. The implication of stress and performance bell curve: If the stress rises from low to medium level, the performance of the people is affected in a positive direction and increases the ability to take action. If stress is higher than moderate, the performance of the people begins to fall (Allen, Hitt & Greer, 1982; Robins & Judge, 2013).

There are some studies on the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and stress (Karabay, 2014; Jain & Cooper, 2012) and organizational effectiveness and stress (Allen, Hitt, & Greer, 1982; Beehr & Newman, 1978). However,

no studies have been found that examine the relationship between stress, OCB, and school effectiveness. From this point of view, it is thought that the current study is important in terms of educational management literature.

2.1 Method

2.2 Research Model

It is appropriate to use the relational research model when focusing on examining possible relationships between two or more variables in the work to be done (Creswell, 2012). In this study, a causal comparison model, one of the relational research models, was used to determine the relationship between variables. Causal comparative research aims to identify the already existing causes or consequences of differences between or among groups (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2006). This model is a model that focuses on the causal comparison to determine the effect of independent variables on dependent variables. There are at least two variables that affect each other in this model. In the causal model, it is tried to show which of these variables is influenced by the other (Cohen & Manion, 1994). The current research is dealt with as organizational citizenship behavior and stress independent variable, and school effectiveness as dependent variable, and the relations between these concepts are examined in the context of cause-effect.

2.3 Universe and Sample

The universe of the research is composed of 7634 teachers working in the province of Elazığ in the academic year of 2017-2018. A simple unselected sampling method was used to determine the teachers who would give feedback in the research. The main feature of this method is that the sample is likely to represent the universe (Buyukozturk et al., 2011). In this sampling method, all units in the universe have an equal and independent chance to be selected for the sample. Within the scope of the research, the opinions of 265 teachers who were working in the schools that were determined as randomly were also taken. 43 of the collected scales were not evaluated because they were randomly or half-filled. Thus, a total of 222 scales are available and validated. It is seen that the universe represents the sample with 90% confidence level with 5.44% error. 65.5% (n = 145) of the teachers participated in the research are female and 34.5% (n = 77) of them are male; 45.3% (n = 101) are married and 54.7% (n = 121) are single; 77.6% (n = 172) have a bachelor's degree and 9.9% (n = 22) continue to the bachelor's degree and 12.6% (n = 28) are graduate students.

2.4 Data Collection Tools

"Stress Scale", "Organizational Citizenship Scale" and "School Effectiveness Scale" were used to collect data within the scope of the research.

A. Stress Scale

The scale was developed by Karakus (2013). The scale consists of one dimension consists of four items. Assessment of the scale is in the form of 4 likert. Karakus (2013)

calculated the internal consistency coefficient of the scale to be .70. The Stress Scale is rated between (1) absolutely disagree and (4) completely agree. The scale with single factor structure is provided with Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). As a result of the analysis, the goodness fit indices were calculated as $\chi^2 = .10$, $df = 2$, $RMSEA = .0000$, $SRMR = .0021$, $GFI = 1.00$, $AGFI = 1.00$, $NFI = 1.00$, $NNFI = 1.01$, $CFI = 1.00$ and $IFI = 1.00$. In this study, internal consistency coefficient was found as .88.

B. The Organizational Citizenship Scale

The scale was developed by Podsakoff et al. (1990) and used in several studies (Karabey 2005; Stone, 2010; ve Erdogan and Bear 2013) in Turkey. In this study the scale form used in Bell and Mengüç (2002) study. The scale consists of five dimensions: Altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue and sportsmanship. There are 4 items to measure each dimension and there are a total of 20 items in the scale. The scale is rated between (1) absolutely disagree and (5) completely agree. In this study, the internal consistency coefficient of the scale was calculated as .94.

C. School Effectiveness Scale

The one-dimensional and eight-item scale developed by Hoy (2009) and was adapted to Turkish by Alanoglu (2014). The internal consistency coefficient (.90) was used in the analyzes to determine the structural validity of the scale. According to CFA the goodness fit indices ($\chi^2 / df = 4.972$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .87$, $CFI = .97$, $NFI = .96$, $RMSEA = .126$ and $SRMR = .043$) were acceptable. The scale was rated between (1) absolutely disagree and (5) totally agree. Internal consistency coefficient was calculated as .94 in this study.

2.5 Data Analysis

The purpose of relational studies is to identify and measure relationships between variables or group scores using correlational statistics. Particularly, correlation and regression analyzes allow testing of relationships between scores obtained and showing the predictability of variables (Creswell, 2012). In this study, it is aimed to show whether stress levels experienced by teachers and OCB predict school effectiveness or not. For this purpose, SPSS 22 package program was used for analyzing collected data, and correlation and multiple regression analyzes were performed. In the analyzes, two categorical variables (gender, marital status, education status) were coded as a dummy variable. Dummy variable is variable that is created when a second and second order variables are reduced to one variable group to create a variable with two levels in the statistic. (Can, 2013).

Before analysis is performed, it should first be checked whether the data are normally distributed. For this, descriptive analyzes of the collected data were made and the skewness and kurtosis coefficients were examined. Findings related to the analyzes made are as in Table 1.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis Table for Scales

	N	$\bar{X}$	df	Skewness	Kurtosis	
School Effectiveness	222	4.84	1.208	-.566	-.162	
Stress	222	2.65	.888	-.043	-.809	
OCB	Altruism	222	4.05	.733	-.997	1.084
	Courtesy	222	4.31	.616	-1.216	1.935
	Conscientiousness	222	3.92	.712	-.746	.344
	Civic Virtue	222	4.01	.699	-.758	.343
	Sportsmanship	222	4.16	.693	-.987	1.436

According to the skewness and kurtosis values in Table 1, it can be said that the data are normally distributed. Because according to Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) these values range from +1.5 to -1.5. Since the data were normally distributed, Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis were used. In this study, school efficacy was dependent variable, demographic characteristics, stress and organizational citizenship behavior were independent variables. The absolute value of the correlation coefficient is defined as "high" level if it is between .70 and 1.00, "medium" level if it is between .50 and .70, and "low" level if it is less than .50 (Buyukozturk, 2012).

In order to obtain accurate results from multiple regression analysis, it is necessary that the variables exhibit normal distribution, there is not a high level of relationship among the independent variables, and there is no correlation between the error terms. For this reason, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is used to determine multiple correlations between independent variables (Can, 2016). In this study, all of the VIF values were found to be less than 10 in the analyzes. In addition, the correlation between error terms is examined to determine whether or not regression analysis should be performed. So the Durbin Watson (d_w) value was checked. The value of this statistic is between 0 and 4 and there is no correlation between the error terms as it is around 2, which means that there is no autocorrelation problem in the developed model. If value is close to 0 indicates high positive correlation, value is close to 4 indicates high negative correlation. In this study it can be said that the Durbin Watson value calculated is close to 2 ($d_w = 1.89$).

3. Findings

In this section, the data obtained from the scales applied in the research process are analyzed and presented. For this reason, firstly a correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between school effectiveness and teachers' demographic characteristics, organizational citizenship behavior and stress levels. The results of the analysis are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix between School Effectiveness Scale, Dimensions of Organizational Citizenship Scale, Stress Scale and Demographic Variables

	OCB1	OCB2	OCB3	OCB4	OCB5	S	G	MS	Sn	ES	E
SE. School Effectiveness	.15*	.28**	.22**	.33**	.33**	-.19**	.02	-.04	.10	-.07	.07
OCB1. Altruism	1	.68**	.45**	.47**	.60**	-.17*	.01	.09	-.10	.06	.10
OCB2. Courtesy		1	.55**	.54**	.61**	-.15*	-.04	.03	-.06	-.03	.13
OCB3. Conscientiousness			1	.53**	.47**	-.26**	-.03	.03	-.19**	-.07	.16*
OCB4. Civic Virtue				1	.54**	-.21**	.01	-.04	-.03	-.03	.06
OCB5. Sportsmanship					1	-.14*	.04	.09	-.07	-.01	.05
S. Stress						1	-.02	.15*	-.16*	-.08	.02
G. Gender							1	-.15*	.22**	.14*	-.10
MS. Marital status								1	-.45**	-.12	.24**
Sn. Seniority									1	.34**	-.34**
ES. Education status										1	-.06
E. Experience											1

When the data in Table 1 are examined, it is seen that school effectiveness is significantly and positively correlated with all dimensions of teachers' organizational citizenship behavior. According to this; there is low, positive and significant relationship between school efficacy and altruism ($r = .15$; $p < .05$), courtesy ($r = .28$; $p < .01$) and conscientiousness ($r = .22$; $p < .01$) and there is middle, significant and positive change between school effectiveness and civic virtue ($r = .33$; $p < .01$) and sportsmanship ($r = .33$; $p < .01$). It is also seen that there is a significant and opposite correlation between school effectiveness and stress ($r = -.19$; $p < .01$). Findings show that as the school effectiveness increases, the stress level of the teachers decreases and the tendency to exhibit more OCB increases. In other words, as school effectiveness decreases, the teachers' stress level tends to increase and tendency to exhibit organizational citizenship behavior decreases.

It is seen that there is a statistically significant and opposite relationship between teachers' OCB and stress. Accordingly, there are low, significant, and opposite relationship between stress and altruism ($r = -.17$; $p < .05$), courtesy ($r = -.15$, $p < .05$), conscientiousness ($r = -.26$; $p < .01$), civic virtue ($r = -.21$; $p < .01$) and sportsmanship ($r = -.14$, $p < .05$). That is, teachers tend to exhibit more OCB as the stress level of teachers decreases, or they tend to exhibit less organizational citizenship behavior as the stress levels of teachers increase.

It is seen that while there is no statistically significant relationship between the school effectiveness and the demographic characteristics of the teachers, only there are opposite, low and significant relationship between conscience and seniority ($r = -.19$; $p < .01$) and positive, low and significant relationship between conscience and experience ($r = .16$; $p < .05$). There is positive, low and significant relationship between stress and marital status ($r = .15$; $p < .05$) and opposite, low and significant relationship between stress and seniority ($r = -.16$; $p < .05$). That is, as the age of the teachers increases, the stress levels decrease. It is also achieved that the stress levels of single teachers and senior teachers are lower.

Table 3 shows the results of multiple regression analysis to determine whether stress, OCB and demographic characteristics of teachers are significant predictors of school effectiveness.

Table 3: Results of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing Relation between School Effectiveness, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Stress Levels and Demographic Characteristics

Predictive Variables	R	R ²	R ² Change (ΔR^2)	F Change p	β	Standard Error	B	t	P
Standard					2.13	.80		2.688	.008
Step 1	.18	.03	.01	.188					
Gender					.03	.175	.011	.159	.873
Marital status					-.02	.182	-.008	-.111	.911
Seniority					.03	.015	.172	2.088	.038
Education Status					-.22	.126	-.124	-1.738	.084
Experience					.24	.143	.119	1.663	.098
Step 2	.25	.07	.04	.008					
Stress					-.24	.091	-.179	-2.663	.008
Step 3	.45	.20	.16	.000					
Altruism					-.28	.150	-.168	-1.853	.065
Courtesy					.27	.191	.139	1.428	.155
Conscientiousness					-.02	.140	-.011	-.132	.895
Civic Virtue					.32	.141	.186	2.283	.023
Sportsmanship					.40	.152	.232	2.668	.008

According to the findings in Table 3, demographic characteristics (gender, marital status, seniority, education status and experience) entered in the first step of the analysis seem not to be a significant predictor of school effectiveness. ($\Delta R^2 = .01$; $p > .05$). However, when the significance levels of the regression coefficients of the demographic variables are examined, it is understood that the seniority variable ($\beta = .03$; $p < .05$) is a significant predictor of school effectiveness. Stress entered in the second step of the analysis seems to be a significant predictor of school effectiveness. ($\Delta R^2 = .07$, $p < .01$). In addition, when the level of significance of the regression coefficient is examined, it is understood that stress ($\beta = -.24$; $p < .01$) is a significant predictor of school effectiveness. When controlling the effect of other variables, it can be said that 7% of the school effectiveness can be explained by the stress experienced by the teachers. As the stress level of teachers increases, the effect of school effectiveness decreases.

OCB (altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, civic virtue, and sportsmanship) entered in the third step of the analysis seems to be a significant predictor of school effectiveness ($\Delta R^2 = .16$, $p < .01$). When the significance levels of the regression coefficients are examined, it is understood that the civic virtue ($\beta = .32$; $p < .05$) and sportsmanship ($\beta = .40$; $p < .01$) are significant predictors of school effectiveness. However, it is seen that altruism ($\beta = -.28$; $p > .05$), courtesy ($\beta = .27$; $p > .05$) and

conscience ($\beta = -.02$; $p > .05$) are not significant predictors of school effectiveness. When the effect of other variables is controlled, it can be said that 16% of school effectiveness is derived from teachers' OCB. That is, as the level of teachers' organizational citizenship behavior increases, school effectiveness also increases.

4. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendation

This study, in which was conducted to investigate the explanation of school effectiveness by the teachers' demographic characteristics, organizational citizenship behaviors and stress levels, firstly, correlation analysis was performed to determine the relationships between these variables. According to the analysis results, school effectiveness was found to be significantly and positively correlated with all dimensions of teachers' OCB. While there is a weak, positive and meaningful relationship between school effectiveness and altruism, courtesy and conscientiousness, it is seen that there is a moderate, meaningful and negative relationship between school effectiveness and civic virtue and sportsmanship.

In Cooper's (2010) study, it was concluded that there was no significant relationship between efficacy measured by student achievement and OCB but there was significant relationship between OCB and school effectiveness according to teachers' perceptions. Cooper (2010) and Talebloo (2015) reported a moderate positive correlation between school effectiveness and OCB. Similar studies examining the relationship between OCB and efficacy in the literature; it is concluded that OCB has significant effects on organizational performance (Podsakoff & MacKenzie, 1994) and school effectiveness (Ozdevecioglu, 2003; Martinez, 2012). In the study conducted by Alanoglu and Demirtas (2016), it was concluded that OCB had a significant effect on school effectiveness and was an important determinant of school effectiveness. In a study conducted by Popescu and Deaconu (2013), it was found that OCB, which is considered as an innovative approach in schools, provided new perspectives to students and has an important and effective tool for the participants in educational processes. In addition, according to the opinions of teachers in the study conducted by Gokmen (2011), it is seen that OCB is an important variable in terms of school effectiveness. According to the results of all these studies, it is important that teachers behave in an organizational citizenship in schools that want to be effective. For this reason, it can be said that effective schools should find solutions to improve teachers' the organizational citizenship behaviors. OCB is perhaps not a decisive component for efficacy alone, but it does not seem likely that schools whose teachers do not display organizational citizenship behavior are likely to be effective.

As a result of the correlation analysis, it is seen that there is a weak, meaningful and reversal (negative) change between school effectiveness and stress. Allen, Hitt and Greer (1982), and Greer and Castro (1986) found negative relationship between stress and perceived organizational effectiveness. The results of the present study and studies conducted in the literature can be interpreted as the fact that the stress of the employees caused a decrease in the level of organizational performance and effectiveness. In

addition, Hoseini, Razavi and Khademi (2014) found no significant relationship between stress and organizational effectiveness. This result can be explained with Robins and Judge's (2013) expression that as the relationship between stress and job performance is a bell curve or inverse U shape. In fact, it can be normal to consider that stress to a certain level does not have a significant effect on effectiveness.

There is a statistically weak, meaningful, and inverse relationship between teachers' OCB (all dimensions) and the stress they experienced. Based on this finding, it can be said that as the stress level of teachers decreases, OCB increase. Karabay (2014) found that job stress is negatively related to both courtesy and conscientiousness dimensions of OCB. Jain and Cooper (2012) found that stress is negatively related to all dimensions of OCB. In general, studies in the literature show that high OCB causes low stress. In other words, it can be said that teachers, who tend to exhibit organizational citizenship behavior, have lower stress levels. But, in Bolino and Turnley's (2005) study, it was revealed that there was positive moderate correlation between OCB and stress in their study. This result can be interpreted as the tendency to show OCB raises the stress levels of teachers in some cases.

It was seen that there was no statistically significant relationship between the school effectiveness and the demographic characteristics of the teachers. With this finding, it can be said that there is no relationship between school effectiveness and demographic characteristics. In Greer and Castro's (1986) study, it was revealed that there was positive correlation between efficacy and age. Alanoglu (2014) concluded that there was no significant relationship between gender, education level, branch, age, experience, and school effectiveness. In the study done by Kusaksiz (2010) gender and education, status variable caused significant differences in the sum of effective school dimensions and seniority variable caused significant difference in all dimensions of effective school. There is no conclusive integrity in studies conducted in the literature on the relationship between effectiveness and demographic characteristics. To perceive of the effectiveness, which has a broad scope and is defined in different ways, may have led to this differentiation.

There was a weak, inverse and significant relationship between conscientiousness and seniority, which is one of the organizational citizenship behaviors of teachers. There was a positive, weak and significant relationship between conscientiousness and experience. In Alanoglu's (2014) study, age and experience variables together affect all dimensions of OCB at a low level and positively. Gender and educational status variables did not cause any significant difference in the dimensions of OCB.

In current study, it was seen that there was low, positive and significant relationship between the stress experienced by teachers and marital status; and there was low, negative and significant relationship between stress and seniority. In other words, as the age of the teachers increased, the stress levels decreased, and single and senior teachers were found to have lower stress levels. In Ozturk's (2001) study it was found that gender variable did not cause any significant difference in the level of stress experienced by teachers, while other demographic variables (age, seniority, branch,

school type and size of school) affected the level of stress. It was determined that teachers, in lower age, experienced more stress and the stress level experienced by teachers decreases as their age and seniority increases.

Multiple regression analysis was performed to determine whether the stress, OCB and demographic characteristics of teachers were significant predictors of school effectiveness. According to the results of the analysis, it was found that the demographic characteristics (gender, marital status, age, seniority, etc.) that entered the first step in the analysis were not a significant predictor of school effectiveness but according to the level of significance of the regression coefficients, only the seniority variable was a significant predictor of school effectiveness. In the opinion of teachers, it is observed that the impact of demographic characteristics on school effectiveness is limited. This shows that demographic characteristics do not affect the effectiveness level of the school. Alanoglu (2014) concluded that gender, educational status, age and seniority variables did not separately affect the school effectiveness, but age and seniority variables together affected school effectiveness at low level and positively.

The stress was added to the analysis in the second step and stress variable was a significant predictor of school effectiveness and explained 7% of school effectiveness. It can be interpreted that as the level of stress experienced by teachers increases, the effectiveness of school decreases. In the third step, the dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior were added to the regression analysis, and it was found that the dimensions were significant predictors of school effectiveness and accounted for 16% of school effectiveness. According to the regression coefficients, it was observed that civic virtue and sportsmanship were significant predictors of school effectiveness, whereas altruism, courtesy and conscience were not significant predictors of school effectiveness. Gokmen (2011) found that teachers' OCB were important in terms of school effectiveness. In the study conducted by Alanoglu and Demirtas (2016), OCB was found to be a significant predictor of school effectiveness. The results obtained in the current study are in parallel with these studies. This result shows that it is very important for teachers to show OCB to create effective school environments.

Teachers' behaviors that will be beneficial to the development of the school, or avoiding the behaviors that they think are harmful for schools, will have important consequences for the realization of the school's objectives. The school that increases the level of achievement of its aims can be defined as effective school. Therefore, encouraging organizations to show organizational citizenship behavior can have significant consequences in terms of organizational effectiveness. In addition, considering the impact of teachers' organizational citizenship behaviors on the effectiveness of schools, studies should be conducted to encourage teachers to show these behaviors in order to create effective school environments. To reduce the stress variable that is concluded to have a negative effect on school effectiveness to the minimum level in schools, the necessary information should be provided by the MoNE in order to eliminate the stress sources (stressors) that cause stress.

In the literature, there are limited number of studies on organizational behaviors affecting school effectiveness and investigating the relationship between school

effectiveness and stress. Qualitative and quantitative studies on organizational behaviors and examining the relationship between stress and school effectiveness can be recommended to perform to the researchers.

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